

A Holistic Demand Flexibility Profiling Framework for the Energy Management Environment

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ABSTRACT

With the increased involvement of new market actors in the operation of modern distribution grids, namely prosumers, aggregators, distribution system operators (replacing distribution network operators), retailers, etc., there will be more sources of uncertainty in distribution system studies. Therefore, more detailed monitoring and analysis of behaviour of different actors and their assets will be required with special focus on the incorporation of demand side as an active element of the electricity grid. The goal of the paper is to present a holistic demand flexibility framework, as a back end application running to support Demand Response Aggregator business role. More specifically, the goal of this paper is to design load models and their behaviour when subject to demand response events, towards establishing a holistic modelling approach that takes into account demand capabilities to participate in alternative demand response strategies that aim both at network operation and market participation optimization.

INTRODUCTION

Inelasticity of Demand along with the continuously increasing presence of distributed intermittent energy sources pose significant challenges and undoubtedly have considerably negative impact on the overall grid balance (SEDC, 2017). Non-forecastable variable generation from RES is causing critical challenges in grid management at all levels while network stresses continuously necessitate for costly upgrades towards increasing capacity and flexibility. Demand Response is a means that can efficiently contribute in various power system ancillary services like regulation or load-following, delivering much higher real-time value than traditional peak load management. However, current DR practices are based on highly centralized control and heavily depend on continuous consumer interaction, thus exhibiting considerable complexity on the central level and significant drawbacks in terms of real-time applicability and response capacity on grid events. Undoubtedly, wide spread utilization of DR within power grid regulation services, necessitates for the deployment of robust and cost-efficient technological solutions that will allow for automated demand coordination on a minute-to-minute basis. What's more, this needs to be performed in a way that minimizes consumer interaction as well as consumer discomfort.

In fact, Ruff (2002) argues that by establishing mechanisms for price-responsive demand responding to wholesale spot prices, can significantly reduce the total costs of meeting demand reliably. Faruqui and George (2005) examine how residential and small to medium commercial and industrial consumers effectively reduced peak energy demand following time-varying prices. However, Orans et al. (2010) suggest that current energy market operations and pricing schemes, have no significant effect on actual demand, especially in the residential sector. One important limitation of traditional demand models is their strong focus on average rather than real-time or even peak demand which arise on an hourly, daily, weekly or seasonal basis. Moreover, there are numerous circumstances where occupants are not directly affected by building costs, rendering price as an ineffective means of demand side management.

Subsequently, demand flexibility must be viewed in its full context, taking into account all realtime environmental and behavioural parameters that eventually define the shape of demand. Future DSM strategies should safeguard consumer preferences while also being able to respond to realtime market conditions (even using market prices as a trigger). Torriti, J. (2011), provided a thorough assessment of occupancy elasticity, as an underlying factor of demand elasticity, arguing that demand loads are predominantly determined by the timing of human presence and activities (e.g. travelling to work, taking

children to school) rather than prices. Detailed findings on occupancy elasticity provide a clear path for potential DSM strategies based on estimated occupancy levels and activities. Overall, energy use is influenced by energy-related behaviours which are distinguished between purchase, usage, and maintenance related behaviours. As Delmas Et al. (2013) argue, effective and long lasting DSM strategies should continuously consolidate unconscious aspects of people’s everyday choices and preferences. Thus, offering intelligent, integrated and personalized energy services through various modalities and communication channels should be among the highest priorities of future DSM strategies.

The goal of the paper is the design and specifications analysis of the Holistic context aware demand flexibility framework, as a back end application running to support aggregator business role. The flexibility profiling mechanism enables the delivery of Context-Aware Flexibility Profiles, reflecting real-time demand flexibility as a function of multiple parameters, such as time, device operational characteristics, environmental context/ conditions, energy cost and occupant comfort preferences. The development of the proposed Holistic Demand Flexibility Profiling Framework is performed as part of the work in E.U. projects NOBELGRID (646184) and MOEEBIUS (680517), while the evaluation is part of the demonstration activities in several E.U. counties and different building types (residential and commercial building premises).

A CONTEXT AWARE DEMAND FLEXIBILITY PROFILING FRAMEWORK

We present a holistic framework for demand modelling, forecasting and control, based on the premise that demand flexibility (the amount by which demand can be actually adjusted) can ultimately be derived from consumer utility functions that quantify consumer discomfort caused by these adjustments. To this end, our framework, attempts to deliver accurate, “context aware” consumer flexibility profiles, that are generated and are continuously adapting to low-level sensor and consumption data. Consumer flexibility profiles, define the extent to which demand can be adjusted while most importantly, quantify the cost of these deviations in terms of consumer discomfort. Defining and quantifying in real-time the “boundaries” and “cost” of demand flexibility, can deliver critical information to any automated demand control and optimization strategy.

Starting with DER modelling, the DER models contain the mathematical formulas for the calculation of electric demand (consumption) of each DER type as a function of dynamic (input data) and static (configuration) parameters affecting DER’s operation. For example: the DER model for a HVAC system contains the mathematical model that calculates the power consumption of the HVAC given HVAC characteristics (rated power, efficiency, thermal characteristics of the building) and some inputs that change dynamically (temperature set point, outdoor temperature etc.). In addition to energy consumption data, the enhanced DER models defined in the project further incorporate as an output parameter the impact of each DER on external environmental condition. The loads to be modelled will have greater capacity to provide flexibility, namely HVAC and lighting devices, as the ones more appropriate and favourable with respect to DR capacity.

Along with the definition of DER model parameters, the proposed framework is considered as context driven, and thus the incorporation of human preferences and environmental conditions is a main prerequisite for the definition of flexibility profiling engine. Therefore, the objective is to define occupants’ comfort profiling models that could be further incorporated in the algorithmic process towards the extraction of DER flexibility values. Thermal and visual comfort profiles are defined associated with the operation of the aforementioned controllable devices. We select the Bayesian networks as the algorithmic framework for extraction of comfort profiles. While the detailed framework for the extraction of occupants’ behavioural profiles is reported in (Malavazos et al, 2014), the focus of this presentation is on the detailed presentation of semantically enhanced DER models to support the holistic demand flexibility framework.

Light Device Type

The light device model is defined as: “consumption as a function of status and dimming level”. Therefore, the learning model is based on the definition of the average consumption values for the different device status and dimming levels.

$$P^{\text{output}} = \text{Nomnal_P} \cdot \text{Status} \cdot \text{Dim_Level} \quad (1)$$

A regression analysis is considered to correlate input (dimming level & device status) and output (power consumption) parameters towards correcting the configuration factors. Linear regression attempts to model the relationship between two

variables by fitting a linear equation to observed data. One variable is considered to be an explanatory variable, and the other is considered to be a dependent variable. A linear regression line has an equation of the form $Y = a + bX$, where X is the explanatory variable and Y is the dependent variable. The slope of the line is b , and a is the intercept (the value of y when $x = 0$). Once a regression model has been fit to a group of data, examination of the residuals (the deviations from the fitted line to the observed values) allows the modeller to investigate the validity of assumption that a linear relationship exists.

The complex part of the learning process is the extraction of the device impact on illuminance level, (towards the provision of enhanced DER profiles). Caicedo et al. proposed a framework for the disaggregation of illuminance levels on ambient luminance and luminance contribution from lighting devices. We consider a lighting system in an indoor office, with N light sources and the associated luminance sensors. The average net illuminance W_m at a single (m th) zone in the zone, given that the lighting system is at dimming vector d , may be written as

$$W_m = V_m(d) + U_m \quad (2)$$

Where $V_m = H_{m,n} * d_n$ and U_m are the illuminance contributions due to lighting system and daylight at the m th zone, respectively. Here, $H_{m,n}$ is the illuminance contribution to the average on the m th zone when the n th light source is at maximum intensity. Denote H to be a matrix whose (m,n) th element is $H_{m,n}$. Illuminance values at the workspace place cannot be measured; only illuminance measurements at light sensors are available following the sensor installation as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Illuminance at workspace plane

Therefore, the measured illuminance at a light sensor in the ceiling is the net illuminance due to contributing light sources and daylight reflected from the objects (e.g. furniture) in the office. Denote $E_{m,n}$ the measured illuminance at the m th light sensor when the n th light source is at maximum intensity, in the absence of daylight. We assume that the illuminance scales linearly with the dimming level. This assumption holds well for practical light sources, e.g. LED light sources. The net illuminance at the m th sensor at the ceiling, given that the lighting system is at dimming vector d and under daylight, can then be written as

$$I_{dm}(d, S_m) = \sum_{n=1}^p E_{m,n} * d_n + S_m \quad (3)$$

Where $\sum_{n=1}^p (E_{m,n} * d_n)$ is the illuminance due to the lighting system and S_m is the illuminance due to daylight measured at the m th sensor on ceiling. In any case, the impact on illuminance is calculated as the linear impact of illuminance from lighting system plus daylight illuminance level. To sum up, the enhanced DER model is defined by 1) load profile as a function of dimming level 2) the impact on illuminance level as a function of dimming level following the algorithmic process presented above.

HVAC Device Type

About HVAC system performance, we are adopting the model proposed in (Bashash et al, 2011) (Kamgarpour, 2013) towards modelling and controlling thermostatically controlled loads for participation on demand side management strategies. The dynamic behaviour of the temperature θ_t of a thermostatically controlled cooling-load (TCL), in the ON and OFF state and in the absence of noise, can be modelled by:

$$\dot{\theta}(t) = -\frac{1}{CR}(\theta - \theta_{amb} + PR), \text{ when ON State} \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{\theta}(t) = -\frac{1}{CR}(\theta - \theta_{amb}), \text{ when OFF State} \quad (5)$$

Where θ_{amb} is the ambient temperature, C is the thermal capacitance, R is the thermal resistance, and P is the power drawn by the TCL when in the ON state. In steady state, **the cooling period** drives a load from temperature θ_+ to temperature θ_- . Thus solving with initial condition $\theta_0 = \theta_+$ gives

$$\theta(t) = (\theta_{amb} - PR) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{CR}}\right) + \theta_+ e^{-\frac{t}{CR}} \quad (6)$$

The same approach is considered for **heating** where for rated power is -P. Therefore, the calculation of final temperature is a mixture of input context conditions (indoor air temperature & ambient air temperature) and configuration parameters (C, R, P & Set-point). The learning process consists at the extraction of C, R parameters that set the thermal demand parameters of each building zone examined. Taking into account HVAC historical data for a short training period, the configuration parameters C, R are calculated.

Demand Flexibility Profiling Framework

The next step of the work is the incorporation of comfort profiles to DER modeling process towards the extraction of demand flexibility profiles. The algorithmic framework towards the extraction of context aware demand flexibility profiles is presented in the following:

```

for i=1:Devices
  for j=1:Setpoint
    Actual_Consumption(j)=DER_Model(Device(i), Setpoint);
    Baseline_Consumption(j)=DER_Model(Device(i), Current_Setpoint);
    Context=DER_Model(Device(i), Setpoint);
    Comfort(j)=Building_Comfort(Device(i),Context);
    Flex_Amount(j)=Baseline_Consumption(j)-Actual_Consumption(j);
  end
end

```

Where, **Setpoint**: is the operational point of each Device, **Context**: is the impact of device operation on environmental conditions, **Comfort**: is the instance of comfort profile as presented above, **Flex_Amount**: the amount of demand flexibility associated with the specific set point operation. We are setting the modelling framework for any controllable device in the smart home environment.

By taking into account the “Flex_Amount” and “Comfort” model parameters, we may further select the optimal control strategies (Setpoints definition) considering business (Demand Response) and contextual (comfort constrains) objectives. We presented above the overall modeling framework towards the definition of context aware demand flexibility profiles. The next section is focusing in real life demonstration and evaluation of the proposed framework.

REAL LIFE DEMONSTRATION AND EVALUATION ANALYSIS

The overall evaluation of the proposed framework will take place in five pilot sites around Europe (UK, Italy, Serbia, Portugal and Belgium), addressing that way different geographical and business characteristics in tertiary and residential premises. Towards the initial evaluation, a full scale lab (protected) environment was established as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Lab Set up

This lab consists of the basic minimum infrastructure (loads as presented above, sensors, actuators, metering equipment and respective software) in a controlled environment to facilitate that way the smooth integration and operation of the heterogeneous elements of the system. Different test scenarios were performed to enable the extraction of accurate demand flexibility profiles.

- **Test 1:** Evaluation of **DER learning** process by taking into account real time and historical data, enhanced with DER semantics as defined above. The analysis shows an accuracy level of **92-95%**, dependent on the data availability during the training process
- **Test 2:** Evaluation of **Comfort Profiling learning** process by taking into account real time and historical contextual data → extraction of thermal and visual comfort boundaries as constrains for demand flexibility profiles
- **Test 3:** Real time **calculation of the potential demand flexibility**, by taking into account the profiles and current contextual conditions → evaluation of different control strategies towards the extraction of maximum **potential demand flexibility** value.

Figure 3 presents the typical load profile of an A/C unit further associated with the DER model characteristics as extracted from the learning process. Nominal Power and duty cycle characteristics are defined from the training process.

Figure 3 HVAC DER model

The same analysis is provided for lighting device modeling. The nominal load profile and the impact on indoor illuminance are derived from time series analysis as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Light DER model

Along with the extraction of typical load profiles, we set the framework for the definition of comfort profiles, thermal and visual. Following training process for a month period, the behavioural profiles are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Thermal & Visual Thermal Profiles

Finally, the extraction of demand flexibility profiles is based on the enhanced DER models, incorporating as constrains of the analytics process the (dis)comfort profiles presented above. The lab environment is the main testbed for the evaluation analysis covering both HVAC and Lighting device types. Heating and cooling are the device types with the highest potential of controllability and subsequently demand flexibility and the results from analytics process are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6 HVAC Device – Demand Flexibility Profile

For the selected timeperiod, the demand flexibility potential (expressed in terms of potential savings) is 9.90 % with Comfort Level Indicator (CLI) over 90% (91.46%).

The same analysis is performed for lighting devices, highlight the dimming and therefore demand flexibility potential, fully preserving end users’ needs and preferences (Potential Savings: 47.41 % with CLI: 84.27 %) as presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Light Device – Demand Flexibility Profile

Table 1 presents the summary results (week period) for the three office zones that consist of the lab environment.

Table 1. Demand Flexibility Potential – Summary

	Thermal		Visual	
	Savings	Comfort	Savings	Comfort
Zone A	9.41%	94.30%	25.10%	95.39%
Zone B	10.01%	92.83%	50.67%	85.62%
Zone C	6.19%	93.89%	35.46%	88.83%

The analysis shows a high level of accuracy on DER and demand flexibility profiling process, enabling that way the establishment of a context aware demand side management framework under different business objectives.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces an innovative framework for automated and personalized control in residential and commercial buildings based on an "event-driven" oriented architecture. The framework is structured around a dynamic behavioural profiling mechanism constantly adapting to real-time events and ambient information. By incorporating the behavioural profiling mechanism to the overall DER modeling process, we can further proceed with the definition of an innovative context aware flexibility profiling framework that will further enable the implementation of more accurate and fine grained control strategies as part of an automated mechanism.

Pilot assessment indicated more than **10% savings** retaining **comfort levels above 90%**. The thorough evaluation of the proposed framework in large scale demonstration is still in progress. Our future research topics include the extension of

scope of the profiling models, towards addressing other major commercial and residential loads (other than lighting), along with appropriate integrated building control strategies.

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NOMENCLATURE

SEDC	=	Smart Energy Demand Coalition
RES	=	Renewable Energy Sources
DR	=	Demand Response
DSM	=	Demand Side Management
DER	=	Distributed Energy Resources
HVAC	=	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
TCL	=	Thermostatically Controlled Load
CLI	=	Comfort Level Indicator

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